

FULL-ENVELOPE FUZZY LOGIC CONTROL

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Abstract

This paper addresses the development of a full-envelope controller for nonlinear systems based on the fusion of ideas from linear control theory and Fuzzy Logic. The term Model-Based Fuzzy Logic Control has been coined to describe this dynamic compensation approach. The Model-Based Fuzzy Logic Controller is essentially a bank of Fuzzy Logic controllers with the composite control input smoothed by a linear compensator. The proper Fuzzy controller in the bank is chosen by a measurement of the magnitude of the reference input, and the linear compensator is determined based on a linearized model of the nonlinear plant. It is shown that the resulting controller provides full-envelope control of the highly nonlinear benchmark plant.

1 Introduction

Linear control methods have limited applicability to the control of nonlinear plants. Small perturbation analysis of a nonlinear plant, for example, results in a linear plant model describing the dynamics of state perturbations about a nominal operating/equilibrium point, and allows application of conventional LTI control to nonlinear problems. The linear controller, however, will only be valid to the extent that the small perturbation assumption is not violated, and the linearized models cannot be used to predict the extent of their own validity. Further, state measurements available at the physical plant and control signal level will not, in general, be the perturbation quantities upon which the compensator is based. The value of the perturbations must be inferred from full state measurements and knowledge of the equilibrium point.

This paper addresses the application of linear control methods to nonlinear plants through the use of Fuzzy Logic. The resulting control approach is referred to as Model-Based Fuzzy Logic Control (MBFLC), and can be successfully used to control a benchmark nonlinear plant throughout a specified envelope of operation. The overall controller architecture is that of a Fuzzy Logic

Controller. Unlike conventional Fuzzy Logic Controllers, however, which primarily entail static compensation [4, 5], in this paper the control of nonlinear dynamic plants will be addressed through the application of dynamic compensation and Fuzzy Logic control concepts.

2 Linear Control of Benchmark Nonlinear Plant

The utility of Fuzzy Logic within the MBFLC framework will be to address the modeling errors that arise between linear compensation and the nonlinear plant. In order to unambiguously measure the performance of the hybrid compensator a low-order, analytic, but highly nonlinear benchmark plant model was utilized for controller development studies. The state-space model for this second-order nonlinear benchmark plant is given as:

$$\dot{X}_1 = -X_1 + X_2 \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{X}_2 = -X_1^3 + U^3 \quad (2)$$

$$Y = X_1. \quad (3)$$

Given an equilibrium state for the nonlinear plant, "small" perturbations in the states about this equilibrium are governed by linear dynamics. A linearized model, then, can be developed to describe these perturbations by using the Jacobian matrices evaluated at the proper equilibrium, $\bar{X}_{1o} = \bar{X}_{2o} = \bar{U}_o$. For Eqns (1) - (3), the linearized dynamical system is [6]:

$$\dot{x}_1 = -x_1 + x_2 \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -3\bar{X}_{1o}^2 x_1 + 3\bar{U}_o^2 u \quad (5)$$

$$y = x_1. \quad (6)$$

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Since $\bar{X}_{1o} = \bar{X}_{2o} = \bar{U}_o$, a new quantity τ can be defined as $\tau = 3\bar{X}_{1o}^2 = 3\bar{U}_o^2$. Therefore, the linearized model becomes:

$$\dot{x}_1 = -x_1 + ax_2 \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\tau x_1 + \tau u \quad (8)$$

$$y = x_1. \quad (9)$$

As long as a single equilibrium point is chosen, τ is a constant and the Laplace domain transfer function for this state space model $P(s) = C(sI - A)^{-1}B + D$ is:

$$P(s) = \frac{\tau}{s^2 + s + \tau}. \quad (10)$$

Two points should be mentioned regarding this plant selection which will bear on the design of a successful controller:

1. When describing the operation of the nonlinear plant as a time-varying linear plant (by allowing τ to vary as $3\bar{X}_{1o}^2$), the value of τ changes rapidly relative to the eigenvalues of the linearized model.
2. *The linearized plant becomes uncontrollable at $Y = 0$.* As $Y \rightarrow 0+$ the gain associated with the linearized model (10) $\rightarrow 0$.

A linear compensator for this plant can be developed via Guillemin-Truxal [3] based on the transfer function of (10). A conceptually straightforward compensator is:

$$G(s) = \frac{19.5(s^2 + s + \tau)}{s^2 + 5s}. \quad (12)$$

Table 1 shows that the linear compensators are only effective over very small regions of state space. In order to achieve an expanded envelope of operation, it is reasonable to ask if a linear compensator can "hand over" the nonlinear plant to a second linear compensator about a different equilibrium at the appropriate time.

The concept of a compensator "handing over" control of a plant to another compensator in mid-trajectory has been demonstrated for the case of linear compensators driving a linear plant [6]. When attempted with a nonlinear plant, however, plant/compensator modeling errors cause the method to fail. The accumulation of error sources can be appreciated by examining the

Figure 1: State space trajectory of nonlinear plant driven by hybrid nonlinear/Fuzzy Controller. Projections of trajectory shown

state trajectory of a successful *nonlinear* controller. A nonlinear controller for the dynamic system of Eqns (1) and (2) can be easily developed using dynamic inversion (DI) concepts [6]. This compensator yields precisely the desired second-order response for the benchmark plant, with $M_p = 1.12$ and $t_s = 1.62$ secs. The state-space representation of the closed-loop DI system transitioning from $Y = 3$ to $Y = 4$ is shown in Figure 1. The dotted line in the Figure is the locus of equilibria, $X_{1o} = X_{2o} = U_o$.

The optimal trajectory, then, based on the DI controller, departs dramatically from the regions of linear compensator validity. Therefore, errors induced by a linear-like compensator can be expected to be significant. It is clear, then, that one function of the Fuzzy Logic in the MBFLC must be to regulate the control signal into the nonlinear plant, either at the input to the plant itself or at the input to the compensator. Assuming that Fuzzy Logic will be incapable of performing this task flawlessly, a second function of Fuzzy Logic will be to account for the unintentional dynamics induced in the plant. Because of the relative ineffectiveness of linear compensation applied to the plant under consideration, it is reasonable to expect that the Fuzzy Logic elements within the MBFLC will dominate.

3 Fuzzy Augmentation of Linear Compensation

From the above discussion, it is clear that only two linear-like compensators will have a direct bearing on the success of the hybrid controller corresponding to the initial and final condition of the plant. It can also be shown that the two compensators required are *not* the linear compensators based upon appropriate perturbation models [6].

An analogous approach is to utilize a bank of Fuzzy Logic Controllers, using linear compensation to ensure a smooth control input response. This compensation scheme employs two elements to facilitate successful control:

1. Trajectory Generator. This is a linear compensator with the input error signal weighted by Fuzzy Logic to reflect a commanded operating condition which is beyond the region of effectiveness of the compensator.
2. Settling Term Generator. This is a Fuzzy Logic controller which compensates for the unmodeled dynamics induced by the Trajectory Generator.

3.1 Trajectory Generator

The error signal E input into the linear compensator is based on the difference between the current and desired plant output. By feeding E directly into a compensator the tacit assumption is made that the compensator being driven is *valid* between the initial and the final states. For a nonlinear plant, this assumption is not true, and feeding the entire E signal into a single linear compensator contributes significantly to the response errors. To overcome this, E must be scaled to account for the limited validity of the linear compensators. This is the purpose of the *Fuzzy Limiter*.

The location of the Fuzzy Limiter is shown in Figure 2. The Figure shows a SIMULINK® simulation of a linear compensator driving the nonlinear plant of Eqns (1) and (2), with the error signal to the compensator modified by the Fuzzy Limiter. The operation of the Fuzzy Limiter is somewhat akin to the "squashing function" action in neural networks.

Figure 2: Closed-loop simulation of linear compensator ($Y=0.6$) driving the nonlinear plant. The error signal is modified by the Fuzzy Limiter, a nonlinear squashing function

The internal structure of the Fuzzy Limiter block is shown in Figure 3. The tuning parameters for the Fuzzy Sets are given in Table 2. In this case, the Fuzzy Logic is used to determine a "penalty factor" for large error signals.

The rules for determining the appropriate weighting factor have single premises. The rules represented in the Figure are of the form: IF $|Error|$ is X_i ; THEN Weighting Factor is Y_i , for $i = 1 \dots N$. N is the number of Fuzzy Sets defined within the Fuzzy Limiter, X_i is a potential value for the magnitude of the error signal, and Y_i is the penalty factor between 0 and 1. Ten such Fuzzy Sets are used in the MBFLC for the benchmark plant.

The operation of the Fuzzy Limiter $W(E)$ is summarized as follows:

- The error signal E is input to the controller.
- The absolute value of the error signal is used to define the universe of discourse. The Fuzzy Limiter is only concerned with the magnitude of the error signal and how it compares with the region of attraction of the linearized compensator.
- The magnitude of the error is evaluated for membership in ten Fuzzy Sets. The membership functions for these sets are shown in Figure 4 and given by:

$$\mu_i(x) = e^{-\frac{(x-x_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2}}, \quad (13)$$

where $i = 0 \dots N$ when N is the number of

Figure 3: Structure of SIMULINK block Fuzzy Limiter

Fuzzy Sets, \bar{x}_i represents the mean or center point of the function for Set i and σ_i^2 is a variance-like term expressing the spread of the function.

- The membership value for each set is multiplied by a weighting factor implied by that Set. This produces the *solution set*.
- The crisp weighting factor is determined by the defuzzification algorithm of [8]:

$$U(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^9 x U_i \mu_{U_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^9 \mu_{U_i}} \quad (14)$$

- The original error function, sign and magnitude, is multiplied by the weighting function.

The penalties implied by each Fuzzy Set are shown in Table 2. These values are based on an estimate of the error being introduced by an Error signal of the given magnitude and are refined through closed-loop simulation. The initial estimation of error is obtained by analyzing the (nonlinear) terms which are neglected in developing the linearized plant model [6].

Figure 5 shows the closed-loop response of the nonlinear plant to a step input $R_{ref}(t) = 0.6 + u_{-1}(t)$ with the Fuzzy Limiter in place. It is clear from the Figure that the tendency of the response to overshoot M_p has been eliminated. Errors are still present, however, in the form of lightly damped oscillations due to control errors.

Figure 4: Membership functions for Fuzzy Sets in Fuzzy Limiter

3.2 Settling Term Generator(s)

The Fuzzy Limiter/Linear Compensator is capable of producing the correct initial transient response in the closed-loop system, given an adequate number of Sets within the Fuzzy Limiter (determining the "adequate" number of sets is addressed in the next section). It is unable, however, to drive the system to steady-state upon reaching the desired output, as shown in Figure 5. Unaccounted-for dynamics – the culmination of mismodeling between the linear controller and the nonlinear plant – continue to effect the nonlinear plant. Further, the error signal is small in magnitude, allowing the Fuzzy Limiter very little control authority. Therefore, an auxiliary control signal is required to drive the plant to a quiescent condition.

The undesired oscillations can be eliminated by introducing Settling Term Generators, which are designated $C_i(t)$. Two rules are required to govern when each Settling Term Generator is to be applied:

1. IF Error is Not Zero AND \dot{Error} is not Positive THEN $U = U_{lin}$
2. IF Error is Zero AND \dot{Error} is Positive THEN $U = U_{lin} + C_i(t)$

Figure 5: Closed-loop response of nonlinear system compensated by Fuzzy Bank

The correct $C_i(t)$ is chosen from a bank based on the magnitude of the commanded input. The overall structure of the controller, then, is essentially a Fuzzy Logic Controller with two possible control actions: 1) Output the exact value of U_{lin} produced by the Fuzzy Bank, or 2) Output the exact value of U_{lin} produced by the Fuzzy Bank, plus the Settling Term $C_i(t)$. The form of each $C_i(t)$ is based on the response of a bank of two pre-weighted linear compensators, as discussed in [6]. This waveform can be approximated using Fuzzy Sets *Eis0* and *EisPositive*. The membership functions for these Fuzzy Sets are shown in Figure 7.

The operation of *Eis0* is straightforward: The set will be activated when the Error signal is at or near 0. The Fuzzy Set *EisPositive* indicates when the system is approaching the reference value from a negative value of Error. This can be seen from the fact that $\dot{E} = (ref - Y) = -\dot{Y}$. When Y initially begins climbing \dot{Y} is positive so \dot{E} is negative. \dot{E} will only become positive when the Y has reached its peak overshoot and started back down towards the reference value. As the system settles out at $Y = Ref$, the Set *EisPositive* reaches a steady-state value of membership, in this case $\mu_{EisPositive} = 0.35$.

The desired function shape is obtained using the Fuzzy AND operation, discussed in [8]. The result of the ANDing procedure is shown in

Figure 6: Desired form for $C(t)$ based on linear analysis of pre-weighted compensator bank

Figure 8. The resulting function reasonably approximates the function shown in Figure 6 for an arbitrary starting time. The exact form of the Fuzzy-derived $C(t)$ can be altered by the tuning parameters of the Fuzzy Sets and a constant weighting term χ , called the Fuzzy Offset. \bar{x} and σ^2 are used to dictate the point in time at which the $C(t)$ function peaks as well as the steady-state value of *Eis0* AND *EisPositive* when the error signal is zero. Of course, the form of *EisPositive* must be maintained such that it cancels the initial peak of *Eis0*, as shown in the Figure. Simulation is currently required to maximize the $C_i(t)$ damping effect for a given step input.

The form of the Banked Model-Based Fuzzy Logic Controller for a step input of known magnitude, incorporating the Settling signal, is shown in Figure 9. By proper tuning of the Fuzzy parameters associated with this design, the oscillations in $Y(t)$ can, indeed, be eliminated for a given initial condition and step magnitude. The tuning data for these two Fuzzy Sets *Eis0* and *EisPositive*, obtained through simulation, is given in Table 3. The magnitude of $C(t)$ is determined by the Offset Value χ . χ is also determined through simulation, and in this case, $\chi = 0.13$.

Figure 7: LEFT: Membership function for E is Zero. RIGHT: Membership function for E is Positive

3.3 Full-Envelope Control

The final step in developing the MBFLC is to develop full-envelope capability by defining a bank of Settling Term Generators. Consider the initiating compensation for a desired envelope of operation from $Y = 0.6$ to $Y = 0.7$ (the results can be generalized for an arbitrary envelope). The single linear compensator is based on the highest possible gain requirements of the plant, in this case for $Y = 0.6$. The system is very *insensitive* to the form of the linear compensator, as long as it is stable and equal order over equal order.

The system is very *sensitive* to the form of the $C(t)$ signal. Small errors in the shape of the Fuzzy Sets E is Zero and E is Positive or in the offset term χ lead to degraded system response. Therefore, similar to the Fuzzy Limiter, the required $C(t)$ function for various step magnitudes within the envelope of operation must be developed in order to achieve full-envelope performance.

The procedure for determining the appropriate number of $C(t)$ generators and the number of Sets within the Fuzzy Limiter is very similar. In fact, tuning for both is done in tandem, starting from the smallest-valued equilibrium point in the desired envelope.

Figure 8: $C(t)$ function formed by ANDing of Fuzzy Sets E is 0 and E dot is Positive

For simulation, the effect of a bank of $C(t)$ generators was implemented using look-up tables. Look-up tables are needed for χ (offset), $\sigma^2_{E \text{ is Positive}}$, $\bar{X}_{E \text{ is Positive}}$, and $\sigma^2_{E \text{ is Positive}}$. The results of the table look-up was then fed into a generic $C(t)$ generator. This information also could have been expressed by Fuzzy Sets, using a bank of $C(t)$ generators with Fuzzy weighting to perform the interpolation. The look-up tables serve to simplify the simulation. Look-up tables are limited in that they can only perform linear interpolation, while a Fuzzy weighting approach could have been tuned just as the Fuzzy Limiter to enhance performance.

The response of this system to step inputs of various magnitudes is shown in Figure 10. The principle difference between the response of this closed-loop system and that of the model response (second order response with $M_p = 1.12$ and $t_s = 1.62$ seconds) is that the system peaks slightly later than desired.

4 Performance Comparison

The simulations shown in Figure 10, conducted on the benchmark nonlinear plant, demonstrate that the MBFLC is capable of obtaining linear-like response from the nonlinear plant such that it falls within established design specifications. Hence, the MBFLC is a success.

The performance of the MBFLC was compared to the DI-based controller and to an alter-

Figure 9: SIMULINK implementation of Banked MBFLC

nate compensator based on Quantitative Feedback Theory (QFT). QFT is a robust controller synthesis technique which can be used to develop a fixed controller based on a family of linear plants [3, Chap 22]. QFT can be applied to the control of a nonlinear plant provided that the piecewise linearization assumption holds (see section 2). By judicious choice of the family of linearized plants, a successful compensator can be developed using QFT for the benchmark plant.

The MBFLC approach shows promise when compared with the DI and QFT compensators. Figures 11 and 12 compare the responses derived from applying QFT and DI with that from the MBFLC. These Figures show that the MBFLC delivers performance approximately equivalent to the DI compensator for the nonlinear plant given a specified region of operation. The QFT based compensator yields an overdamped response.

5 Conclusions

Most of the current work in Fuzzy Logic Control is of a *static* nature. That is, Fuzzy Logic Controllers have the character of nonlinear PID controllers. Many conventional control design approaches entail *dynamic* compensation. In this work we have strived to blend Fuzzy Logic methods and dynamic compensation into a single control approach. The initial hybrid linear/Fuzzy controller concept was based on the use of mul-

Figure 10: Closed-loop response of Full-Envelope MBFLC to step inputs of various magnitudes

multiple linearizations of a nonlinear plant. Linear compensators based on the linearized plants were to produce multiple plant control outputs, which would then be blended together using Fuzzy Logic to produce a composite control signal. This control signal would then be further weighted by a Fuzzy assessment of the validity of the controller bank.

Equilibrium	Maximum Step
0.1	0.000025
0.2	0.00022
0.3	0.0008
0.4	0.002
0.5	0.004
0.6	0.0075
0.7	0.0097
0.8	0.01
0.9	0.013
1.0	0.018
1.1	0.02
1.2	0.03

Table 1: Maximum step magnitude away from equilibrium facilitated by linear compensators

Figure 11: Closed-loop responses for QFT-based design and MBFLC design

Figure 12: Closed-loop responses for Dynamic Inversion-based design and MBFLC design

Fuzzy Set	Mean	Variance	Implicate(Penalty)
E is 0.0	0.0	0.000021	1.0
E is 0.014	0.014	0.000021	0.6
E is 0.028	0.028	0.000021	0.56
E is 0.042	0.042	0.000021	0.48
E is 0.056	0.056	0.000021	0.44
E is 0.07	0.07	0.000021	0.41
E is 0.084	0.084	0.000021	0.38
E is 0.098	0.098	0.000021	0.37
E is 0.112	0.112	0.000021	0.35
E is 0.126	0.126	0.000021	0.34

Table 2: Tuning Parameters for Fuzzy Limiter Membership Functions

Fuzzy Set	Mean	Variance
\dot{E} is 0	0.0	0.0000074
\dot{E} is Positive	0.064	0.000021

Table 3: Tuning Parameters for Fuzzy Sets E is Zero and \dot{E} is Positive

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